

MM-LDTF: Multi-Model Legal Document Translation Framework for Vernacular Languages

Samik Goyal DAV Public School, Patiala
samikgoyal@gmail.com

Abstract—This paper presents a novel framework designed to significantly enhance the quality of legal document translations. By utilizing an LLM to pre-process the text before it is translated, the framework showed substantial gains in terms of quality and accuracy of translations over current solutions such as SUVAS, Google Translate and Microsoft Azure AI Translator on Indian Judgments. This framework also ensured consistent and accurate formatting in the output document, which other AI tools did not.

I. INTRODUCTION

India has a vast linguistic landscape with 22 scheduled languages in the Constitution[1]. However, the judiciary operates in English[2], creating a language barrier for the vast majority of the population who are not proficient in legal English. More than 99.9% of the Indian population cannot understand English in its legal context[3]. As a result, many citizens cannot access judicial decisions, understand legal proceedings, or engage fully with the legal system.

Existing translation tools struggle with legal documents due to their inability to properly handle documents, formatting, and artefacts from digitisation processes. These limitations often result in inaccurate translations that misrepresent legal meanings or make no sense.

In this paper, a novel approach that employs a large language model (LLM) to pre-process legal texts before translation has been presented. By refining and fixing the text structure, this prepares the document for more accurate translation by subsequent models and maintains good formatting. This multi-model framework significantly improves translation quality and preserves the document’s formatting and legal nuances.

The framework introduced in this paper shall be referred to as MM-LDTF hereinafter.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Despite efforts to make legal documents accessible in multiple languages, existing solutions have notable shortcomings. These tools often fail to recognise sentences properly, especially in scanned documents with poor formatting, leading to fragmented and inaccurate translations. Such limitations motivated me to explore alternative approaches that could overcome these challenges.

A. Challenges in Legal Document Translation

Legal documents, especially older judgments, frequently contain artefacts from scanning and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) processes. They also do not have a standardised

format in which they are written. These artefacts, combined with complex legal language and non-standardised formats, pose significant hurdles for conventional translation models.

III. RELATED WORK

The Supreme Court has developed the Supreme Court Vidhik Anuvaad Software (SUVAS) to translate legal judgments into vernacular languages. There are also 2 very popular general-purpose AI document translation tools: Google Translate and Microsoft Azure AI Translator.

A. SUVAS: Supreme Court Vidhik Anuvaad Software

SUVAS is based on Project Anuvaad[4], which is open source. It uses a custom-trained Tesseract for OCR to detect text inside the document and CRAFT for the line detection[5].

B. General-Purpose Translation Models

General-purpose translation services like Google Translate¹ and Microsoft Azure AI Translator² have made significant advancements in natural language processing and translation. Since they are closed source, their architecture has not been analysed. That is why it was decided to survey MM-LDTF against these systems.

C. Already translated by the court

The Hon’ble High Courts have also translated some landmark judgments by both the High Courts and the Supreme Court. These were translated using human translators. They were aided by SUVAS in some cases. The amount of judgments translated into Hindi is quite high. However, the counts for other languages are quite low with most languages having less than 1000 judgments translated³[6].

IV. LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT SOLUTIONS

A. Improper sentence segmentation

This issue involves translation tools being unable to recognize sentence boundaries. They are unable to mark sentence starts and ends. This causes them to divide a single sentence into multiple parts before translating it. For example, if a sentence spanned across two lines, in many cases, it was broken into two parts, and then those parts were translated

¹Available at <https://translate.google.com/>

²Available with Microsoft Azure AI services at <https://azure.microsoft.com/>

³As on 2 February 2024

independently. This caused the resulting translation to be very poor. For example:

at Hyderabad for the State of Telangana and the State of Andhra Pradesh, whereby the High Court dismissed the Criminal Petition

was interpreted as two different sentences and translated to:

तेलंगाना राज्य और आंध्र राज्य के लिए हैदराबाद में
(For the Telangana State and Andhra State, in Hyderabad)

प्रदेश, जहाँ उच्च न्यायालय ने आपराधिक याचिका खारजि कर दी
(Pradesh, where the High Court dismissed the Criminal Petition)

When concatenated, these don't make sense. This issue occurs frequently with SUVAS. MM-LDTF does not have this issue, as it uses an LLM to identify the sentence starts and stops.

B. Failure to identify which words should be spelt out or translated/transliterated

All of the current translation systems do not understand which words should be spelt out or translated/transliterated⁴. For example:

- *CrPC* should become सी. आर. पी. सी. (Spelt out)
- *Negotiable Instrument Act* should become नेगोशिएबल इंस्ट्रूमेंट अधिनियम (transliterated)
- *J U D G E M E N T* should become नर्णय (translated)

Usually, the words with all letters capitalised were spelt out and others were translated/transliterated. The problem is that judgments, a lot of the time, have headings completely capitalised. For example, this heading was taken from a Supreme Court Judgment:

J U D G M E N T

Figure 1. Capitalized heading sample

All the systems including MM-LDTF couldn't consistently recognize when transliteration should be done instead of translation. However, MM-LDTF does recognize when words should be spelt out vs translated/transliterated.

C. Overlapping Issue

This issue only occurred with Google Translate. This issue caused the translated text to be overlaid on top of the original document, rendering it unreadable. This issue mainly occurred with scanned judgments. However, it was quite common occurring in 42.11% of the judgments translated in the survey. An example has been given in Figure 2.

⁴The names of Bare Acts only have valid translations for Hindi. Therefore they can be both translated(as long as the valid translation is used) or transliterated for Hindi. However, for all other languages, they should be transliterated. SUVAS uses a glossary for Hindi translations of Act names and only has this issue with non-Hindi languages

is satisfied that there is a substantial question of law. On facts, High Court without formulating substantial question of law allowed the appeal and set aside the judgment passed by the trial court and the first appellate court. High Court failed to notice mandate of S. 160 while deciding a second appeal – Thus, the judgment passed by the High Court is set aside – Matter remitted back to the High Court to first

Figure 2. Overlapping text sample from Google Translate

D. Poor Formatting

This issue affected the three systems in varied amounts. Sometimes, the output translation would have very poor formatting, with uneven text sizes and no justification. This affected Google Translate a lot. Microsoft Azure AI Translator didn't have this issue.

E. Slow Speed

SUVAS was incredibly slow in comparison to other systems. It sometimes took over 15 minutes to translate a 10-page document.

F. Failure to correct grammatical and spelling errors

All of these systems can trip on grammatical errors. This issue affects SUVAS the most. This usually arose from bad OCR. For example, *prison bars* in the picture below is recognized as *prison ba:rs*:

prison bars.

These sorts of artefacts from OCR can mess up the current translation systems. Usually older judgments have to be digitised using OCR, while newer ones are directly typed on a computer.

V. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework uses a dual-model approach: First, an LLM pre-processes the source text, and then a normal translation model translates it sentence by sentence.

A. Framework Overview

The framework comprises two main components: an LLM-based pre-processing module and a translation module. The LLM pre-processes the input legal document, addressing issues such as incorrect sentence segmentation, formatting inconsistencies, and artefacts from digitisation. It also fixes the issue of whether it should be translated, transliterated, or spelt out. The cleaned text is then passed to a translation model, for translation into the target vernacular language.

B. Architectural Design

The LLM is prompted/fine-tuned to make multiple changes to the text. These changes are:

- It should clean up the text. This fixes the artefacts issue.
- It should correct grammatical/spelling errors. This fixes issues where the OCR is not able to identify the text correctly.
- It should correct Capitalization (For spelt out/transliteration/translation issue).
- It should convert the text into HTML. This allows MM-LDTF to maintain formatting even after translation.

MM-LDTF first uses the LLM with the above instructions to pre-process the text. Then, the code goes over the HTML tags and translates the sentences one by one. After this, the HTML is rendered into a PDF.

C. Key Innovations

The primary innovation is the utilization of an LLM for pre-processing legal texts. This approach effectively addresses all the challenges posed by complex legal texts and poor document formatting, which are not adequately handled by existing translation tools.

D. Current Implementation

For conducting the survey, a prompted *GPT-4o* model was used for the LLM module. The full prompt which was used can be found inside "gptCleaner.py" from Appendix A. The *IndicTrans2*[7] model was used for the translation module. All the code was written in Python, and evaluations were done on a laptop with the Nvidia RTX 4070 Mobile Graphics Card. The code used for evaluations is provided in Appendix A.

VI. METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the effectiveness of MM-LDTF, a comprehensive survey was conducted involving 26 evaluators across 12 languages. All the evaluators in the survey were either Judges, Law Professors, Lawyers, PhD Scholars, or Students from National Law Universities.

A. Data Collection

A dataset of 76 legal judgments was collected along with their official translations provided by the court. These were collected from the official websites of the Hon'ble High Courts and the eSCR⁵ portal. The selection included both recent and older judgments, covering a variety of formatting styles and digitisation artefacts. It also included judgments on a variety of topics.

B. Experiment Setup

The judgments were translated using MM-LDTF, Google Translate, and Microsoft Azure AI Translator.

⁵eSCR is a portal which hosts a copy of High Court Judgments and Supreme Court Reports. It is available at <https://judgments.ecourts.gov.in/>

Table I
AVERAGE SCORES OF EACH TRANSLATION SYSTEM ACROSS ALL THE METRICS

	Formatting	Accuracy	Fluency
Google	1.12	1.43	1.43
Azure	2.36	2.59	2.53
MM-LDTF	3.70	3.61	3.75
Court	4.07	3.99	4.04

C. Survey Design

Legal experts proficient in 12 vernacular languages were engaged to evaluate the translations. The languages surveyed were: *Assamese, Bengali, Dogri, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Malayalam, Manipuri, Marathi, Punjabi, Tamil, and Telugu*

Each evaluator assessed the translations based on three criteria: formatting, accuracy, and fluency. The survey aimed to gather quantitative and qualitative feedback on the effectiveness of MM-LDTF compared to existing models.

VII. EVALUATION METRICS

To objectively assess the translation quality, three evaluation metrics were employed. All of them are on a scale of 1 to 5. If a translation model failed to translate at all, it was given a 0. The exact instructions which were given to the evaluators are available in Appendix B. The metrics are:

A. Formatting

This metric assesses the visual presentation and layout of the translation. It includes aspects such as text alignment, font consistency, proper use of bolding, italics, headings, bullet points, numbering, and overall adherence to formatting standards.

B. Accuracy

This metric assesses how precisely the translation conveys the meaning of the source text. An accurate translation faithfully represents all the information, nuances, and intent of the original text without omissions, additions, or distortions.

C. Fluency

This metric assesses the readability and linguistic quality of the translation in the target language. A fluent translation reads naturally and is free from grammatical, syntactic, and typographical errors, making it easily comprehensible to the reader.

VIII. RESULTS

In all the figures and tables presented, Google Translate has been shortened to Google, and Microsoft Azure AI Translator has been shortened to Azure. Court represents the official translation by the court.

Figure 3. KDE Plot of Formatting Ratings

Figure 6. Violin Plot of Formatting Ratings

Figure 4. KDE Plot of Accuracy Ratings

Figure 7. Violin Plot of Accuracy Ratings

Figure 5. KDE Plot of Fluency Ratings

Figure 8. Violin Plot of Fluency Ratings

A. Comparative Analysis

As the figures and table I show, MM-LDTF beat current solutions such as Google Translate and Microsoft Azure AI

Translator by huge margins in Formatting and Fluency. The

Table II
AVERAGE TRANSLATION COST PER PAGE OF EACH TRANSLATION SYSTEM(IN USD)

	Cost per page (in USD)	Converted Price (in INR)
Google	\$0.0800	₹6.7280
Azure	\$0.0360	₹3.0276
MM-LDTF	\$0.0072	₹0.6055
Court	—	—

difference in accuracy was less; however, MM-LDTF still clearly beat the others.

One of the problems that affect MM-LDTF is that LLMs can be unpredictable. This means that sometimes, it might not produce the correct output on the first try. This could explain the smaller difference in accuracy. With a human proofreader, this problem can be mitigated. However, for the survey, none of the judgments were proofread to ensure a fair comparison.

B. Cost Analysis

The cost per page for Azure and MM-LDTF has been taken as the average cost per page they had in the survey. Google Translate API on the other hand bills the user per page translated and that constant price has been used. The prices for all 3 services were billed in USD and have been converted to INR with the current market rate of \$1 = ₹84.10.

MM-LDTF is substantially cheaper than other solutions as shown in Table II. However, it should be noted that the *IndicTrans2* model runs locally in the case of MM-LDTF which requires powerful hardware. Another thing to note is that OpenAI, the creator of *GPT-4o*, also offers a batch API which returns the translations within a window of 24 hours from the submission of the request for 50% discount on the pricing. The price in the table has been calculated using the normal API and not the one with batch discount.

IX. DISCUSSION

A. Strengths of the Proposed Framework

MM-LDTF demonstrates significant improvements in translation quality and formatting preservation. By pre-processing the text with an LLM, it effectively addresses all the significant issues affecting current AI translation tools. By cleaning up the text, it also reduces the chances of the translation model tripping as compared to conventional translation systems.

B. Comparison with Existing Systems

MM-LDTF fixes most of the biggest problems affecting existing translation systems. However, even this solution still requires a human proofreader and is not fit for autonomous deployment.

C. Practical Implications

The adoption of MM-LDTF can enhance accessibility to legal documents for non-English speakers, promoting inclusivity and equal access to justice.

X. LIMITATIONS

A. Model Limitations

The LLM may sometimes hallucinate, adding or removing information from the text. This issue can usually be solved by a re-run of the model. Therefore, it can be solved easily if a human proofreads the translated document.

The LLM has a limit on the maximum amount of tokens it can output. In the case of *GPT-4o* which is used in this paper, it is 16,384 tokens. This allows the model to process around 30 pages of text. Further work can be done in this regard to allow the LLM to process larger documents in batches.

The translation model can also trip sometimes with more complex sentences with complex wording. This issue usually requires a human to translate the text manually. However, this issue occurs very rarely. This issue is a lot more common with other systems.

The translation model could incorrectly translate Bare Act names. Fixing this issue would require fine-tuning the translation model. However, this issue was very rare as the translation model mostly translated/transliterated correctly.

B. Survey Limitations

Due to SUVAS's extended translation times, it was not feasible to include it in the survey. Additionally, as this research fixes the problems with SUVAS, a direct comparison in the survey may not be necessary.

The survey also covered only 12 of the 22 scheduled languages in India. Although the dataset contained a good number of judgments, it may not cover all legal topics.

XI. CONCLUSION

A. Summary of Contributions

A novel framework has been presented which improves the translation of legal documents by incorporating an LLM-based pre-processing step. This approach addresses the limitations of existing translation tools and improves accessibility to legal documents in vernacular languages.

B. Broader Impact

Implementing this framework can significantly improve access to legal information for non-English speakers, contributing to a more inclusive legal system. This framework can also be deployed in other countries.

This framework also has possible applications outside of Legal Judgment translations.

XII. FUTURE WORK

A. Approach Enhancements

Further improving the prompt of the LLM and possibly fine-tuning it could increase the accuracy and reduce the issues discussed in X-A.

Work can be done to allow the LLM to process longer documents in smaller batches.

The translation model can also be fine-tuned on legal texts to improve the quality of translations in general and fix the translation vs transliteration issue.

The translation model can also be swapped for the Microsoft Azure AI text translation API or the Google Translate API for text translation.

B. Integration with Legal Databases

Integrating the framework with legal databases such as eSCR could facilitate translation and access to legal documents.

C. Applications outside of Legal Judgments

Applications of this framework in translating other types of documents can be explored.

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REFERENCES

- [1] *The constitution of india*, 8th Schedule, Lists the Scheduled Languages officially recognised by the Constitution, 1950.
- [2] *The constitution of india*, Article 348(1), Defines the language to be used in the Supreme Court and High Courts, 1950.
- [3] D. Y. Chandrachud, *Address by the Chief Justice of India at the inauguration of online e-inspection software, Delhi High Court*, Annotation: “English, is a language which is not comprehensible, particularly in its legal avatar, to 99.9% of our citizens”, Jan. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V3FVlm5rxII>.
- [4] EkStep Foundation. “Project Anuvaad: Open-source document translation platform for indic languages.” Accessed: October 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://anuvaad.org/>.
- [5] EkStep Foundation. “Anuvaad: Technology stack.” Accessed: October 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://anuvaad.sunbird.org/learn/technology-stack>.
- [6] “Promotion of hindi in higher courts: Ai assisted legal translation advisory committee assisting translation of e-scr judgments into vernacular languages by using ai tool.” Press release by Press Information Bureau. [Online]. Available: <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=2001863>.
- [7] J. Gala *et al.*, “Indictrans2: Towards high-quality and accessible machine translation models for all 22 scheduled indian languages,” *Transactions on Machine Learning Research*, 2023, issn: 2835-8856. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=vfT4YuzAYA>.

APPENDIX A CODE FOR MM-LDTF

The entire code for MM-LDTF is available from Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14223093>.

APPENDIX B SURVEY DATA AVAILABILITY

All the anonymised results from the survey, code used to generate plots and the instructions that were sent to the evaluators can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14209753>.